

LEARNING STYLES AND STRATEGIES

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Annotation: This article presents knowledge about learning styles and strategies and are able to identify your own learning styles and develop your language learning strategies. Moreover, exploit classroom learning opportunities effectively, and will be more adequately equipped to continue with language learning outside of the classroom.

Keywords: learning styles, language learning strategies, Willing' cluster, Communicative, Analytical, Authority-oriented, Concrete strategies, effective language learner, less effective language learner

Over the last twenty years, there has been growing interest in incorporating a focus on learning strategies and learning-how-to-learn into language curricula. There is a general belief that such a focus helps students become more effective learners and facilitates the activation of a learner-centered philosophy. It is also believed that learners who have developed skills in learning-how-to-learn will be better able to exploit classroom learning opportunities effectively, and will be more adequately equipped to continue with language learning outside of the classroom. Learning is not about cramming in information. It is about learning by doing. It is about looking at issues in various ways and developing capacities, especially the ability to dig below the surface to reach the truth. That is why our goal is to teach students to learn how to learn rather than merely passing information to them.

Learning styles identified four major styles:

- communicative analytical
- authority-oriented
- concrete

These styles were derived from learner strategy preferences, which, in Willing's data, clustered in the following ways.

Communicative: These learners were defined by the following learning strategies: they like to learn by watching, listening to native speakers, talking to friends in English, watching television in English, using English out of class, learning new words by hearing them, and learning by conversation.

Analytical: These learners like studying grammar, studying English books and newspapers, studying alone, finding their own mistakes, and working on problems set by the teacher.

Authority-oriented: The learners prefer the teacher to explain everything, having their own textbook, writing everything in a notebook, studying grammar, learning by reading, and learning new words by seeing them.

Concrete: These learners tend to like games, pictures, film, video, using cassettes, talking in pairs, and practicing English outside class.

Learning strategies are the specific mental and communicative procedures that learners employ in order to learn and use language. Every task and exercise will be underpinned by at least one strategy, although in most classrooms learners are unaware of these strategies. One of the hypotheses being tested by learning strategy researchers is that awareness and deployment of strategies will lead to more effective language acquisition.

Learning styles are general approaches to language learning, while learning strategies are specific ways to deal with language tasks in particular contexts. The research perhaps most closely related to the links between learning styles and strategies are study on the five learning styles contrasts identified in her Style Analysis Survey (SAS):

- visual versus auditory (the use of physical senses for study and work)

- extroversion versus introversion (dealing with other people)
- intuitive-random versus concrete-sequential (handling possibilities)
- closure-oriented versus open (approaching tasks)
- global versus analytic (dealing with ideas).

Each of the five style contrast constitutes a comparative style continuum. It is important for learners to identify these learning styles and recognize their strengths and thus expand their learning potential.

The dominant style of the more effective language learners was communicative. These learners can be characterized as field independent and active. Willing suggests that these learners exhibit a degree of autonomy and goes on to say that “There can be a certain self-directedness involved in deliberately using interactions for learning purposes, and in this way an underlying field-independence may show itself. The dominant style for the less effective language learners, on the other hand, was authority-oriented. These learners exhibit characteristics of field-dependence and passivity. This learner type prefers structure and sequential progression. They do better in ‘traditional’ classrooms and look on teachers as authority figures.

The style profiles appear to reflect other aspects of the survey. The more effective learners were field independent and active in their approach to learning. This is consistent with the finding that the more effective learners spend significantly more time activating their English out of class than less effective learners. A caveat is in order. As already mentioned, the four learning styles identified in the study were represented in both groups, and in fact, the ‘communicative’ and ‘authority-oriented’ groups were represented in the less effective groups in almost equal numbers. That said, it should be noted that more effective learners were four times more likely to provide responses to the survey that were consistent with a communicative style.

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